

THE OUSTMARTED CARD GAME

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GAMES BRIEF

These cards are designed to get you thinking about the intersections between London as a Digital City and your experience as students living and studying in the city. Start by placing these cards within a deck containing the Category Cards you have already been using. Either develop your own game by picking a card from the deck, or choose from one of the following games, which are designed to encourage a group discussion and personal reflection.

Alternatively, if you do the game after the discussion on the maps, you may think of this as a starting point:

"To live well with the digital, we need to understand how to live through the digital. How can the resources, values and knowledge transcend the obstacles and make us more equipped to put forward our values and rights?"

GAME 1

CRITICAL COMMUNITIES

Distribute the cards evenly amongst the players. Each player picks a Key Card and a Category Card and places them face down on the table. Each player then reveals the cards in turn and the discusses how they relate to their experiences of technology and the city.

For example, a player may reveal Knowledge card 1 and Category Card 'Social Media'. The player must then discuss how they know the digital city through social media.

GAME 2

DRAWING CONNECTIONS

Divide the group in half. One half are given the Key Cards, evenly distributed. The other half are given the Category Cards, evenly distributed.

A member of the Key Card group starts by placing one of their cards face up on the table. A member of the Category Card group then follows by placing one of their cards face up on the table. The group then discusses the connections between the cards and how they relate to their experiences and perceptions of London as a Digital City.

KNOWLEDGE

TYPES

How do we know what we know?
(epistemology)

- Evidence
- Intuition
- Rumour
- Tacit
- Embodied
- Biases

KNOWLEDGE

SOURCES

Where does our information come from?

- 'Official' sources
- Social media
- Broadcast media
- Live events
- Friends and family
- Strangers

KNOWLEDGE

SKILLS

How do we use the knowledge we have?

- Problem solving
- Challenging
- Learning
- Invention and innovation
- Developing new skills

KNOWLEDGE

ACTIONS

How do we share knowledge?

- Formal learning environments
- Informal learning environments
- Digitally / Physically
- Implicitly through our actions
- Explicitly through what we say, do and write

KNOWLEDGE

ETHICS / ENVIRONMENTS

What are the ethics of sharing knowledge?

- The power of sharing knowledge
- The power of not sharing knowledge
- Places of knowledge sharing
- People and knowledge sharing
- Objects of knowledge

AGENCY

CAPACITY

How do you recognise your agency in the world?

- What comes easy for you?
- What is difficult for you?
- Why does your agency differ from some one else?

AGENCY

ARRERTION

How do you assert your agency in the world?

- How do you use your agency to make a change in the world?
- How do you use your agency to make a difference in the world?

AGENCY

INFLUENCE

When is your agency affected by others?

- Can you always do the things you want to?
- Do you always have a choice?
- Do you always have free will?

VALUES

PERSONAL & PUBLIC

What are your values?

- Personal values
- Professional values
- Public values

VALUES

EXTERNAL

What are their values?

- Institutional values
- Government values
- Corporate values
- Tech values
- Capital values

VALUES

PRIORITIES

How do you prioritise and make sense of your values?

- Social values
- Political values
- Economic values
- Environmental values

RIGHTS

UNIVERSAL

What are your rights?

- Human rights
- Right to life
- Right to respect
- Right to personal liberty
- Right to education
- Right to a fair trial and due legal process

RIGHTS

DIGITAL

What are your digital rights?

- Right to transparency
- Right to be forgotten
- Right to opt-out
- Right to opt-in
- Right to ownership
- Right to not be tracked

RIGHTS

CIVIC

What are your rights to urban citizenship?

- Right to public space
- Right to privacy
- Right to safety
- Right to move
- Right to vote

FEARS

TYPES

What are your fears?

- Personal
- Public
- Social
- Economic
- Political
- Environmental

FEARS

DIGITAL

What are your digital fears?

- Surveillance
- Privacy
- Security
- Algorithms
- Tracking
- Misunderstandings

FEARS

URBAN

What are your fears of the city?

- Safety
- Crime
- Financial
- Social
- Environmental

